

CONNECT - CONNecting Evidence-based health information and CiTizens

Keywords: Evidence-based; Health information; Citizen Science; Co-creation; Patient-centered; Communication

Scientific abstract

Wider Research Context: The CONNECT project is an extension to the ongoing A+CHIS project, which aims to tailor evidence-based health information (EBHI) to individual information needs. This is vital for informed decision-making and positive health behavior. However, effectively communicating EBHI while maintaining scientific accuracy remains challenging. Citizens often struggle to recognize and evaluate the trustworthiness of health information. This project addresses this challenge through a Citizen Science approach.

Objectives: The objective is to co-create guiding principles to connect what citizens value in health information with established evidence-based quality criteria. Specifically, we aim to explore the public's criteria for trustworthy health information and combine them with scientific criteria, resulting in co-created guiding principles for effectively communicating the significance of EBHI to the public. These principles will assist A+CHIS researchers and relevant stakeholders to communicating EBHI more effectively, making it easier to identify trustworthy sources.

Methods: We will employ a collaborative Citizen Science approach. The project involves work packages for project management, Citizen Scientist (CS) recruitment, exploration of public criteria for trustworthy health information, development guiding principles, and process evaluation. CSs will engage in qualitative data collection and interpretation, culminating in the co-creation of guiding principles during a two-day workshop. Various data validation approaches will be used, alongside a tailored communication plan, to ensure meaningful CS involvement throughout the project.

Level of Innovation: The co-created guiding principles for communicating EBHI will enhance the patient-relevant execution of the A+CHIS project. Collaborating with CSs is an innovative and effective strategy to mitigate "research waste". Our long-term vision is to establish a standing Citizen Scientist advisory group at our Institute. The CSs in this group will contribute to our Institute's research strategies, study designs, and dissemination of results.

Primary Researchers Involved: *Prof. A. Siebenhofer-Kroitzsch*, a leading member of the A+CHIS project, brings expertise in health services research and invaluable links to other Citizen Science environments. In CONNECT, she serves as the principal investigator. *C. Radl-Karimi, PhD* specializes in qualitative data methodologies, and her prior experience with participatory concepts such as co-creation and co-production forms the basis for this Citizen Science project. She will oversee recruitment and project coordination. She will be supported by *N. Berger*, a Research Scientist at IAMEV, who has a background in psychology and public health. *Dr. N. Posch* specializes in health literacy and the promotion of EBHI. In CONNECT, she introduces CSs to the MAPPinfo checklist for assessing EBHI.

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**Institute of General Practice and Evidence-based Health Services Research (IAMEV),
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